

Dynamic learning agenda: A practical example

Problem

Crop Wild Relatives (CWRs) offer great potential for more resilient and diverse agriculture. However, breeders of CWRs face challenges, including technical constraints and limited collaboration and knowledge sharing between key actors.

Solution

The Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA) is a flexible multi-actor method that supports learning and problem-solving through shared activities. It serves to bring breeders and researchers together to co-design, test and adapt solutions.

Benefits

The method improves collaboration between farmers, breeders and researchers, leading to practical, locally adapted solutions, as well as building trust and strengthening knowledge exchange.

Actors and roles

At the project level, the main actors and roles include (see infographic):

1. The **Dynamic Learning Agenda (DLA)** team:
Responsible for overall organisation and the selection and training of project researchers on the methodology. Helps to identify a project-relevant theme and stakeholder group. In this case, plant breeders working with CWRs were chosen.
2. Project **researchers leading** a learning network:
Responsible for using the methodology with their local stakeholder group. In this case five were selected.
3. Other **project researchers**:
Responsible for aligning new research trials with the real-world problems identified during workshops in order to potentially provide actionable solutions.

Applicability box

Theme: Participatory learning, knowledge co-creation, stakeholder engagement

Keywords: Stakeholder collaboration, reflective methodology

Context: Applicable across diverse contexts

Application time: Aligned with project timeline and activities

Equipment: Basic facilitation tools, additional materials depending on the field trial setup

Best in: Collaborative, participatory innovation projects

Step-by-step instructions for researchers leading a learning network

1. Establish a **local learning network** of approximately ten people
 - Identify and connect local and regional stakeholders and practitioners. In this case mostly plant breeders
2. Organise and conduct one **field workshop** each year with your local learning network before the annual project meeting and compile the information gathered
 - Visit a field or trial site together and observe crops and trials directly, discuss local challenges, exchange experiential knowledge
3. Attend one **reflection workshop** each year during the annual meeting organised by the DLA team
 - Reflect on insights from field workshops
 - Compare regional challenges, identify patterns and share successful approaches
 - Take successful approaches and ideas for col-

- laboration back to your groups
- Elevate challenges related to research to the other project researchers
4. Participate in the **iterative learning cycles** by providing continuous feedback to track learning and refine approaches over time
 5. Attend a **final joint reflection** organised by the DLA team to prepare tangible **outputs**
 - Reflect on the overall learning process across regions
 - Identify overarching insights, shared challenges, and effective solutions
 - Co-develop policy, scientific and practitioner outputs

- groups or networks you can connect with.
- Find out who the main contact is for the group or organisation you want to work with – and build a friendly relationship.
- Make sure your events don't clash with other important activities and events (e.g. football matches or local festivals).
- Be ready to adapt – people might show up and not want to do a planned activity. Be open to adjusting your timing, methods, or content.
- Ensure that participants always take away something valuable from the experience.
- Instead of asking groups to come to you, attend meetings or gatherings they already go to.
- Field workshops can happen anywhere something interesting is going on (e.g. where wild wheat or beet is being grown). They don't need to be tied to an official trial or experiment.
- Use simple, open-ended questions.

Tips and tricks

- Don't worry! This process is about building relationships, not being perfect.
- Ask your peers if there are already relevant

Infographic, visualising the method of the dynamic learning agenda.

About this practice abstract and PRO-WILD

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PRO-WILD: The project 'Protect and Promote Crop Wild Relatives - PRO-WILD' is running from September 2024 to August 2029. The overall goal of PRO-WILD is to protect and promote crop wild relatives (CWRs) to enhance the resilience of agriculture to climate change and other environmental and anthropogenic stresses. The project focuses particularly on wild relatives of wheat, sugar beet, and brassicas. It aims to strengthen both *in-situ* and *ex-situ* conservation, identify valuable genetic traits, and facilitate the use of these resources in breeding programs for future-proof agriculture.

Project website: www.pro-wild.eu

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